

Stunting and blood lead levels in a non-industrial rural area: the role of microminerals in child growth risk assessment

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Abstract

Stunting remains a major public health issue in low-resource settings, with emerging evidence linking it not only to nutritional deficiencies but also to environmental toxicants such as lead. Despite this, limited research has explored the interplay between lead exposure, microminerals, and child growth in non-industrial rural areas. This study aimed to investigate the association between blood lead levels (BLLs), essential microminerals (zinc, manganese, and iron), and stunting in children, while also identifying environmental sources of lead. A cross-sectional study was conducted among 58 children aged 0–59 months in Datar Village, Central Java, Indonesia. Anthropometric assessments and venous blood samples were collected, and trace elements were quantified using ICP-MS. Lead content in environmental samples (water, food, foliage, soil, and paint dust) was also analyzed by ICP-MS. BLL ≥ 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dL}$ was found in 55.2% of children, with manganese levels exceeding the safe threshold in 67.2% of children. Normal zinc levels were found in 91.4% of subjects, while iron deficiency was detected in 65.5% of subjects. No significant association was observed between trace element levels and height-for-age Z-scores. Environmental analysis revealed excess lead in spinach, foliage (longan, hairy fruit), soil samples, and some paint dust samples. Elevated BLL and widespread micronutrient deficiencies may co-exist in non-industrial rural environments and contribute to child health risks. Integrated environmental monitoring is recommended.

Keywords

blood lead, environmental exposure, iron deficiency, ICP-MS, rural health, stunting

Introduction

Stunting remains one of the most pressing public health challenges affecting children in low- and middle-income countries (Akbar et al. 2023). Defined as impaired linear growth resulting in a height-for-age Z-score (HAZ) below -2 standard deviations from the WHO Child Growth Standards, stunting

affects approximately 22% of children under five globally, with Indonesia reporting a national prevalence of 21.6% in 2022 and higher rates in rural and socioeconomically disadvantaged communities (Paramitha et al. 2024). The consequences of stunting extend beyond childhood, contributing to increased morbidity, poor cognitive outcomes, reduced productivity, and elevated risks for non-communicable

diseases in adulthood (Lestari et al. 2024). While inadequate nutrition and repeated infections are well-established determinants of stunting, emerging evidence highlights toxic environmental exposures—particularly lead (Pb)—as overlooked contributors to growth retardation (Gleason et al. 2016). Lead is a pervasive neurotoxin that accumulates in the body, with no level of exposure considered safe in children. Although most studies have focused on urban or industrial areas, growing concern exists over rural exposure routes, including drinking water, contaminated soil, traditional cookware, and deteriorated paint, especially where environmental monitoring is limited (Yeter et al. 2022).

Recent international studies have documented elevated blood lead levels (BLLs) in children and their association with impaired growth. In Uganda, a study by Moody et al. (2020) found that 65% of children had BLLs ≥ 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dL}$, and lead was significantly associated with decreased height-for-age scores (Moody et al. 2020). Similarly, Gleason et al. (2020) used causal mediation analysis in a Bangladesh cohort and reported that stunting may modify the neurotoxic effects of lead, with stronger associations observed in stunted children (Gleason et al. 2020). In Mexico, Cantoral et al. (2015) observed that the negative association between lead and child height was more pronounced in zinc-deficient children, suggesting that micromineral status, particularly zinc, may influence the toxicity of lead (Cantoral et al. 2015).

Despite these important findings, few studies have simultaneously examined the interaction between blood lead levels, essential microminerals (e.g., zinc, manganese, and iron), and stunting in rural, non-industrial settings, especially in Southeast Asia (Irwinda et al. 2019). Most research has focused either on lead exposure or on nutritional deficiencies in isolation (Kordas 2017). To date, no integrated study in Indonesia has comprehensively assessed both biological and environmental factors in the same cohort (Córdoba-Gamboa et al. 2023).

This is the first study in a rural, non-industrial Indonesian population to examine the relationship between stunting, blood lead levels, and microminerals, while simultaneously identifying environmental sources of lead exposure (Abdillah 2022; Rodriguez et al. 2024). This study aimed to investigate the association between blood lead levels, essential microminerals (manganese, zinc, and iron), and stunting in children from a non-industrial rural area while identifying environmental lead sources.

Materials and methods

Study design and participants

This cross-sectional study was carried out in Datar Village, a non-industrial rural area located in Banyumas Regency, Central Java, Indonesia. The study population consisted of children aged 0 to 59 months who regularly attended four integrated community health posts (Posyandu). A total of 58 children were enrolled using purposive sampling, comprising 29 stunted and 29 non-stunted

children, as determined by height-for-age Z-scores based on the WHO Child Growth Standards and recorded in their Health Card (Kartu Menuju Sehat [KMS]). Children were eligible for inclusion if their caregivers were literate and willing to participate and if the children were healthy enough to undergo venipuncture. Children with known severe illnesses or medical contraindications were excluded. The study protocol received ethical approval from the Universitas Harapan Bangsa Ethics Committee (Approval No: B.LPPM-UHB/4303/2021), and written informed consent was obtained from all participating caregivers.

Anthropometric assessment and blood collection

Anthropometric measurements were conducted using WHO-calibrated equipment provided by the Banyumas District Health Office. Height was measured to the nearest 0.1 cm using a stadiometer, and weight was recorded using a digital scale. These measurements were used to assess stunting status based on height-for-age Z-scores. Blood samples (3 mL) were collected from the antecubital vein of each child by trained phlebotomists using sterile 3 cc syringes and transferred into EDTA-coated BD Microtainer® tubes. All collections took place at the Posyandu centers under aseptic conditions and were coordinated with local midwives and health cadres. The blood samples were immediately stored in insulated cool boxes maintained at 2–8 °C and transported within two hours to the Pharmacy Laboratory at Universitas Harapan Bangsa, where they were stored at 4 °C prior to further analysis.

Blood sample preparation and ICP-MS analysis

Each blood sample was prepared for analysis by pipetting 200 μL of whole blood and diluting it at a 1:20 ratio with an aqueous solution containing 0.1% Triton X-100 (Sigma-Aldrich, France) and 0.1% ultrapure nitric acid ($\geq 69\%$, Suprapur®, Merck, Germany). The mixture was vortexed for 1 minute and transferred into acid-washed glass tubes to prevent contamination. Prepared samples were shipped on ice to the Center for Health Laboratory (Balai Besar Laboratorium Kesehatan, BBLK) in Jakarta for elemental analysis. Elemental quantification was conducted using Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS, Agilent 7800, Agilent Technologies, USA), equipped with a MicroMist (borosilicate glass) concentric nebulizer, a Scott-type double-pass quartz spray chamber, and a High Matrix Introduction (HMI) system. The temperature was controlled from -5 °C to 20 °C. The system was operated in both helium collision modes to minimize polyatomic interferences. High-purity argon gas (99.999%) was used for plasma generation. Calibration curves for each element were prepared using six-point standard solutions (0.01, 0.02, 0.04, 0.06, 0.08, and 0.1 mg/L) from Merck Certipur® and Agilent, with coefficients of determination (R^2) ≥ 0.999 . Certified reference materials (Seronorm™ Trace Elements

Whole Blood, Sero AS, Norway) were included in each run to ensure analytical accuracy. Instrument control was performed using ICP-MS MassHunter Workstation software. The limits of detection (LoD) and quantification (LoQ) were as follows: Pb, < 0.07 µg/dL and < 0.2 µg/dL; Mn, < 0.14 µg/dL and < 0.5 µg/dL; Zn, < 0.15 µg/dL and < 0.5 µg/dL; Fe, < 0.2 µg/dL and 0.7 µg/dL.

Environmental sampling and analysis

To investigate environmental sources of lead exposure, multiple environmental samples were collected from households and surrounding areas. Drinking water was collected in 600 mL pre-cleaned, acid-washed plastic bottles. Food items, including snacks, vegetables, rice, and fish, were placed in sealed bags, while foliage was gathered from roadside and home garden plants. Soil and wall dust samples were air-dried and homogenized in clean, sealed bags. For heavy metal analysis, 0.1 g of each soil or dust sample was digested in an Erlenmeyer flask with 4 mL of a 5:1 mixture of hydrofluoric acid (HF) and perchloric acid (HClO₄), followed by heating to 260 °C on a hotplate within a fume hood. After the initial digestion, 2 mL of aqua regia (HCl:HNO₃ = 3:1) and 10 mL of 10% aqua regia were added. The cooled digest was transferred into a 100 mL volumetric flask and brought to volume with ultrapure water. All samples were analyzed by ICP-MS using the same instrumentation and analytical conditions as for blood samples.

Statistical analysis

All statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS version 26.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Subgroup analysis by age category (0–23 and 24–59 months) was performed to evaluate cumulative lead exposure. The Shapiro–Wilk test was applied to assess the normality of continuous variables. Blood levels of Pb, Mn, Zn, and Fe were summarized using descriptive statistics (mean, median, and interquartile range). Multiple linear regression analysis was employed to examine associations between metal concentrations and children's height-for-age Z-scores.

Results

Characteristics of the study population

A total of 58 toddlers aged 0–59 months were enrolled and classified into stunted (n = 29) and non-stunted (n = 29) groups based on WHO height-for-age Z-scores. Participants were selected through purposive sampling from four integrated health posts (Posyandu) in Datar Village, Banyumas Regency, Central Java. The village, known for its mountainous terrain and tourism potential, is divided into three RW (community units), each comprising three RT (neighborhood units). Community health services are supported by five health cadres at each integrated health post (Posyandu), a village midwife, a family planning officer (PLKB), and the village head.

Trace elements in blood samples

Blood concentrations of lead (Pb), manganese (Mn), zinc (Zn), and iron (Fe) were measured in all study participants. As presented in Table 1, 32 children (55.2%) were found to have lead (Pb) ≥ 5 µg/dL, with a slightly higher proportion in the non-stunted group (18 of 29) than in the stunted group (14 of 29). Elevated manganese levels (Mn > 2 µg/dL) were detected in 39 children (67.2%), more frequently among stunted children (n = 20). Normal zinc levels (Zn: 234.9–949.2 µg/dL) were found in 91.4% of subjects, while iron deficiency (Fe < 40,000 µg/dL) was found in 65.5% of subjects (see Table 1) (Goullé et al. 2015; Bohn et al. 2023; CDC 2025).

Blood lead (Pb) levels by age group

Lead burden was higher in older toddlers. Table 2 presents the age-specific distribution of BLLs. Among the 32 children with elevated BLLs (≥5 µg/dL), 24 (75%) were aged 24–59 months, compared to only eight in the 0–23-month age group. This suggests a potential age-related cumulative exposure effect.

Table 1. Pb, Mn, Zn, and Fe levels of stunted vs. non-stunted children (n = 58).

Trace element	Category	Stunted (n)	Non-stunted (n)	Total (n)	Reference range
Lead (Pb)	≥5.0 µg/dL	14	18	32	≤ 3.5 µg/dL* (CDC 2025)
	3.6–4.9 µg/dL	11	9	20	
	≤3.5 µg/dL	4	2	6	
Manganese (Mn)	>2 µg/dL	20	19	39	0.9–2 µg/dL** (Bohn et al. 2023)
	0.9–2 µg/dL	2	0	2	
	<0.9 µg/dL	7	10	17	
Zinc (Zn)	>949.2 µg/dL	2	2	4	234.9–949.2 µg/dL **
	234.9–949.2 µg/dL	26	27	53	
	<234.9 µg/dL	1	0	1	
Iron (Fe)	>50000 µg/dL	4	3	7	40.000–50.000 µg/dL*** (Goullé et al. 2015)
	40000–50000 µg/dL	5	8	13	
	<40000 µg/dL	20	18	38	

* CDC 2025 (CDC 2025).

** Bohn et al. 2023 (Bohn et al. 2023).

*** Goullé et al. 2015 (Goullé et al. 2015).

Table 2. Blood lead (Pb) levels by age group.

Age (months)	≥5 µg/dL	3.6–4.9 µg/dL	≤3.5 µg/dL	Total
0–23	8	4	2	14
24–59	24	16	4	44
Total	32	20	6	58

Relationship between trace elements and stunting

A multiple linear regression analysis was performed to evaluate the influence of Pb, Mn, Zn, and Fe levels on height-for-age (HAZ). As shown in Table 3, none of the trace elements were significantly associated with child height (all *p*-values > 0.05). While iron showed the highest standardized coefficient (*Beta* = 0.248), the result was not statistically significant (*p* = 0.260).

Table 3. Regression coefficients of Pb, Mn, Zn, and Fe in relation to child height.

Predictor	Coefficient (B)	Std. Error	Beta	t-value	p-value
Constant	83.477	4.659	–	17.918	0.000
Lead (Pb)	0.521	0.703	0.104	0.741	0.462*
Mn	-0.451	0.354	-0.187	-1.274	0.208*
Zn	-0.125	0.190	-0.148	-0.661	0.512*
Fe	0.003	0.003	0.248	1.137	0.260*

*All *p*-values > 0.05.

Lead in Environmental Sources

Drinking water

As shown in Table 4, all 21 household drinking water samples were collected from four types of sources: village public water supply systems (Perusahaan Air Minum or

PAM), dug well water, refill drinking water, and natural spring water sources. All samples had lead (Pb) concentrations consistently at 0.2 µg/dL, well below the national standard of 1.0 µg/dL. Manganese (Mn) levels ranged from 0.5 to 2.6 µg/dL, remaining within the acceptable limit of 40 µg/dL. Notably, the highest Mn concentration (2.6 µg/dL) was still compliant with regulatory thresholds.

Food and beverage

Table 5 summarizes ICP-MS results. All snack and milk samples were found to contain lead concentrations below the regulatory limit of 0.25 mg/kg. Lead levels in both fish samples were also within acceptable limits, ranging from 0.01 to 0.02 mg/kg, and did not exceed the threshold of 0.30 mg/kg. Among the vegetable samples, spinach leaf was detected to have a lead concentration of 0.40 mg/kg, which exceeded the permitted limit of 0.20 mg/kg. The remaining vegetable samples, including other spinach leaves, carrot, and cabbage, were determined to comply with the regulatory standards. Rice samples were tested and found to contain lead levels between 0.02 and 0.08 mg/kg, all within the allowable range of 0.25 mg/kg. Environmental samples were also analyzed. Most foliage samples were observed to meet the maximum permissible level of 0.20 mg/kg. However, elevated concentrations were identified in longan (0.39 mg/kg) and hairy fruit leaves (0.24 mg/kg), indicating that environmental contamination may have occurred at those sampling points. Moreover, soil samples were evaluated, with lead concentrations ranging from < 0.002 to 230 ppm at all but one site. In the soil sample collected near the main road, a concentration of 730 ppm was detected, which exceeded the regulatory threshold of 400 ppm. Paint dust samples were also analyzed. While several showed non-detectable levels, four samples were found to exceed the allowable limit of 90 ppm, with the highest value recorded at 6100 ppm in house paint dust 1.

Table 4. Pb and Mn concentrations in drinking water from households with BLL ≥ 5 µg/dL.

No	Types of drinking water sources	Pb (µg/dL)	Pb Standard	Mn (µg/dL)	Mn Standard
1	Village public water supply systems/PAM	0.2	1.0	0.5	40
2	Village public water supply systems/PAM	0.2	1.0	0.5	40
3	Village public water supply systems/PAM	0.2	1.0	0.5	40
4	Village public water supply systems/PAM	0.2	1.0	0.5	40
5	Village public water supply systems/PAM	0.2	1.0	0.5	40
6	Village public water supply systems/PAM	0.2	1.0	0.5	40
7	Village public water supply systems/PAM	0.2	1.0	0.5	40
8	Village public water supply systems/PAM	0.2	1.0	0.5	40
9	Village public water supply systems/PAM	0.2	1.0	0.5	40
10	Village public water supply systems/PAM	0.2	1.0	2.6	40
11	Village public water supply systems/PAM	0.2	1.0	0.5	40
12	Dug well water	0.2	1.0	0.5	40
13	Dug well water	0.2	1.0	0.5	40
14	Dug well water	0.2	1.0	0.5	40
15	Refill drinking water	0.2	1.0	0.5	40
16	Refill drinking water	0.2	1.0	0.5	40
17	Refill drinking water	0.2	1.0	0.5	40
18	Refill drinking water	0.2	1.0	0.5	40
19	Refill drinking water	0.2	1.0	0.5	40
20	Natural spring water	0.2	1.0	0.5	40
21	Natural spring water	0.2	1.0	1.5	40

Table 5. Lead (Pb) concentration in food, environmental samples, and paint dust.

Sample category	Sample description	Pb concentration	Regulatory limit	Unit
Food (snacks)	Crackers	0.06	0.25	mg/kg
	Biscuits 1	0.07	0.25	mg/kg
	Biscuits 2	0.04	0.25	mg/kg
	Cereal	0.05	0.25	mg/kg
Food (milk)	Ultra-high temperature (UHT) milk	0.02	0.25	mg/kg
Food (fish)	Catfish	0.02	0.3	mg/kg
	Salted fish	0.01	0.3	mg/kg
Food (vegetables)	Spinach leaf 1*	0.4	0.2	mg/kg
	Spinach leaf 2	0.12	0.2	mg/kg
	Spinach leaf 3	0.1	0.2	mg/kg
	Carrot	0.05	0.2	mg/kg
	Cabbage	0.03	0.2	mg/kg
Food (grains)	Rice sample 1	0.08	0.25	mg/kg
	Rice sample 2	0.02	0.25	mg/kg
	Rice sample 3	0.03	0.25	mg/kg
Foliage	Guava leaf around the main road	0.14	0.2	mg/kg
	Red shoots leaf around the main road	0.14	0.2	mg/kg
	Longan leaf around the main road*	0.39	0.2	mg/kg
	Duku leaf around the main road	0.14	0.2	mg/kg
	Guava Leaf around the house	0.11	0.2	mg/kg
	Longan Leaf around the house	0.06	0.2	mg/kg
	Hairy fruit leaf around the house *	0.24	0.2	mg/kg
Soil	Soil around the house A	<0.002	400	ppm
	Soil around the house B	<0.002	400	ppm
	Soil around the house C	<0.002	400	ppm
	Soil around the house D	<0.002	400	ppm
	Soil around the house E	<0.002	400	ppm
	Soil around the rice fields	230	400	ppm
	Soil around the main road*	730	400	ppm
Paint dust	House paint dust 1*	6100	90	ppm
	House paint dust 2	<0.002	90	ppm
	House paint dust 3	<0.002	90	ppm
	House paint dust 4	<0.002	90	ppm
	House paint dust 5*	380	90	ppm
	School environment paint dust*	3880	90	ppm

* exceed the allowable limit.

Discussion

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study conducted in a non-industrial rural region of Central Java, Indonesia, that comprehensively examines the intersection of blood lead levels (BLL), micronutrient status (zinc, manganese, and iron), and environmental sources of lead exposure in relation to child stunting and trace element toxicity. The results demonstrate a concerning public health scenario: more than half of the sampled children (55.2%) presented with elevated BLLs ($\geq 5 \mu\text{g/dL}$); normal zinc levels (Zn: 234.9–949.2 $\mu\text{g/dL}$) were found in 91.4% of subjects; 67.2% had manganese levels above the upper reference range; and iron deficiency (Fe < 40,000 $\mu\text{g/dL}$) was found in 65.5% of subjects. No statistically significant associations were observed between trace element con-

centrations (Pb, Mn, Zn, Fe) and height-for-age Z-score (HAZ). These biological findings were further contextualized by the detection of lead contamination in several local environmental matrices, including vegetables (particularly spinach), plant foliage (longan and hairy fruit), household soil, and paint dust.

The high proportion of children with elevated BLLs aligns with earlier findings from other Southeast Asian studies, despite our study being conducted in a rural, non-industrial setting typically presumed to be at lower risk for lead exposure (Yimthiang et al. 2019). According to CDC guidelines, the blood lead reference value is 3.5 $\mu\text{g/dL}$; blood lead concentrations $\geq 5 \mu\text{g/dL}$ are considered actionable and are associated with adverse health outcomes, including neurodevelopmental impairment, behavioral issues, and impaired growth (Delgado et al.

2018; Shekhawat et al. 2021). The fact that 32 of 58 children exceeded this threshold is highly concerning and suggests chronic, unrecognized environmental exposure. Stratification by age revealed that children aged 24–59 months had markedly higher BLLs compared to younger toddlers (Yimthiang et al. 2019; Hoang et al. 2021). This supports existing literature identifying increased mobility, greater hand-to-mouth activity, and environmental interaction as critical factors contributing to cumulative lead intake in early childhood (Sharma et al. 2015; Hoffman et al. 2017). However, the absence of a statistically significant relationship between BLL and linear growth (HAZ) in this study mirrors previous mixed findings, where some cohorts showed growth impairment associated with lead, while others found no significant effects (Gleason et al. 2016; Moody et al. 2020; Ahmadi et al. 2022). This discrepancy may reflect differences in exposure dose, chronicity, nutritional status, or genetic susceptibility, and highlights the need for longitudinal follow-up (Muciño-Sandoval et al. 2021; Halabicky et al. 2022; Otavina and Kazakova 2024).

Manganese levels exceeded the safe threshold in 67.2% of children. Although an essential micronutrient, manganese in excess has been increasingly recognized as a neurotoxin (27.28). Elevated Mn levels have been associated with reduced IQ, attention deficit, and behavioral dysregulation, even at subclinical levels (Björklund et al. 2017; Rodrigues et al. 2018). The source of excessive Mn in this population is uncertain, but possible contributors include groundwater contamination, high Mn content in local soils, or overuse of iron-containing supplements (Sharma et al. 2021; Chakraborty et al. 2022). Normal zinc levels (Zn: 234.9–949.2 µg/dL) were found in 91.4% of subjects. Several population-based studies have shown that most children have normal whole blood zinc levels, although zinc deficiency remains prevalent, especially in developing countries or in children with chronic conditions (Wang et al. 2015). Studies in China, Canada, and Europe have shown that 50–70% of healthy children fall within the physiological range of Zn levels, with normal levels being the most common finding (Wang et al. 2015).

Iron deficiency (Fe < 40,000 µg/dL) was found in 65.5% of subjects. Although not all studies use Fe units in µg/dL of whole blood, a recent study by Mushi (2023). (Mushi et al. 2023) showed that iron deficiency is very common in young children, particularly in rural and developing areas, with rates approaching or exceeding 65.5% in certain subpopulations. Studies from India and Bangladesh have consistently shown that the prevalence of iron deficiency in children, especially those aged < 5 years, often exceeds 65%, particularly in groups affected by infection, malnutrition, or low socioeconomic status (Sharma et al. 2021; Chakraborty et al. 2022; Gugloth et al. 2022). Although the unit “Fe < 40,000 µg/dL” is rarely used directly in the literature, the prevalence figures are supported both epidemiologically and clinically (Sharma et al. 2021; Chakraborty et al. 2022; Gugloth et al. 2022).

Environmental sampling identified multiple lead exposure pathways. While all household drinking water samples were within acceptable regulatory thresholds, one spinach leaf sample showed lead levels twice the permitted limit (Nag and Cummins 2022). In addition, foliage from longan and hairy fruit trees—commonly found in household gardens—also contained elevated lead concentrations. This likely results from uptake through contaminated soil or the deposition of atmospheric lead particles (Wang et al. 2016; Cao and Bourquin 2020). Most alarmingly, one household soil sample contained lead at 730 ppm—nearly twice the allowable limit of 400 ppm (Obeng-Gyasi et al. 2021; Filippelli et al. 2024).

In parallel, three of six tested paint dust samples were found to exceed the permissible threshold of 90 ppm, with one sample measuring an extreme 6100 ppm. This level of contamination points to the legacy use of lead-based paint, a problem known to persist in many low-resource settings despite formal regulation (Obeng-Gyasi et al. 2021; Ranjbar et al. 2023). These findings collectively refute the assumption that rural areas are inherently safer from environmental toxins and suggest that informal construction practices, agricultural pesticide residues, and poor environmental surveillance may contribute to hidden lead burdens (Rustin et al. 2016; Goumenou et al. 2021).

This study possesses several notable strengths. It is among the first in Indonesia to integrate biological trace element testing and environmental sampling outcomes into a single analytic framework. The use of high-precision ICP-MS for biomonitoring ensures methodological rigor and data accuracy (Laur et al. 2020). Furthermore, by including both environmental and biological assessments, the study provides a more comprehensive understanding of exposure pathways. Nevertheless, limitations must be acknowledged. The cross-sectional design precludes causal inference, and the relatively small sample size and purposive sampling approach limit generalizability. Lastly, no cognitive or neurodevelopmental assessments were conducted, which could have helped quantify the functional impact of trace element imbalances.

Conclusion

This study highlights a critical but underrecognized burden of environmental lead exposure and micronutrient imbalance among children in a rural, non-industrial region of Central Java. More than half of the participants showed elevated blood lead levels; the majority had excessive manganese concentrations, most had normal zinc concentrations, and many were iron deficient. Environmental sources such as contaminated vegetables, foliage, soil, and legacy paint dust were identified as potential contributors. While no significant association was found between trace element concentrations and stunting, the findings underscore the complex interplay of environmental and nutritional factors affecting child health.

These results call for urgent public health action, including environmental surveillance, micronutrient screening, and early detection of blood lead levels to identify and reduce exposure risks and improve child health outcomes.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: The study protocol received ethical approval from the Universitas Harapan Bangsa Ethics Committee Approval No: B.LPPM-UHB/4303/2021, and written informed consent was obtained from all participating caregivers.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

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Use of AI

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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